

African Mining Economies and the Gender Gap in Political Participation *

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Abstract

There is a significant gender gap in political participation in Africa. At the same time, many African economies are heavily reliant on traditionally male-dominated extractive industries. We investigate whether mining activities influence the gender gap in political participation at the local level. To do so, we use Afrobarometer data for over 150,000 respondents merged with precise geo-located information on mining sites in multiple difference-in-difference estimations. We find the gender gap decreases across four dimensions of political participation: in proximity of mineral deposits with ongoing production, the gap in discussing politics drops 18.4%, voting 67%, attending community meetings 28%, accepting women as leaders 95%. These effects are driven by women near active deposits being more politically active than those living further away. However, we detect no change in the gender gap in attending protests, although this gap does widen in high conflict areas. The results are comparable in an alternative, strictly exogenous identification strategy where we predict changes in mining activities with international commodity prices. The main results hold in areas with net inward, net outward, or net stable migration. We explore several mechanisms and find employment, but not community grievances, to be an important channel explaining changes in women's political involvement.

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1 Introduction

There is a sizeable gender gap in political participation, as women have been historically excluded from politics and sidelined in decision-making (Masad, 2020). Women worldwide are still under-represented in leading positions, both at the national and local level. They are also less likely to engage in formal and informal political activities, from voting and campaigning to discussing politics with others (Isaksson et al., 2014; Gottlieb, 2016). This is particularly problematic as political engagement is an important tool for traditionally dis-empowered groups to make their needs heard, and because women show different policy preferences compared to men (Chattopadhyay & Duflo, 2004; Gottlieb et al., 2018).

While gender imbalances in political representation and participation remain ubiquitous, there are large regional and sub-regional variations. Some countries have progressively approached gender parity, whereas others are still far from meeting the target. Across the African continent, differences in political engagement between men and women remain particularly stark (Isaksson et al., 2014; Lowe-Morna et al., 2021).

Macro-level studies have posited that resource extraction is one of the key factors driving low female political participation in Africa (Awoa et al., 2022; Ross, 2008). The argument holds that extractive industries crowd out female-dominated sectors, increase education inequality across genders and raise fertility rates. In turn, these effects impact women's engagement in politics. If true, challenges in addressing gender disparities in political participation could be further exacerbated across numerous African countries, especially where the mining sector, already a backbone of the national economy, is projected to grow in the coming years.

In contrast to macro-level findings, local-level evidence challenges the presumed negative relationship between resource extraction and female political participation because of the empirical evidence of the potential for women's economic empowerment in mining areas. Yet, no study so far has analyzed the localized effects of mining on women's engagement in politics and, consequently, the gender gap in political participation. In the microeconomics literature, mining expansion is associated with women having more job opportunities in the service sector (Kotsadam & Tolonen, 2016), being less tolerant towards domestic violence and benefiting from improved access to healthcare (Benshaul-Tolonen, 2019, 2023; Guimbeau et al., 2021). These findings show that extractive activities can provide women with opportunities and resources which are conducive to empowerment and could, therefore, translate to increased political participation. Nevertheless, mining has been notoriously linked to several health (Corno & de Walque, 2012), social (Berman et al., 2017; Ahlerup et al., 2020; Fourati et al., 2021) and environmental risks (von der Goltz & Barnwal, 2019), to which women are often disproportionately exposed. The gendered impacts of mining could, arguably, provide women with stronger incentives to voice their grievances through means of political engagement. At the same time, however, the sector has been linked to security concerns, such as corruption (Knutsen et al., 2017), conflict (Berman et al., 2017) and sexual violence (Fourati et al., 2021), which could disproportionately increase the cost of political participation for women. Considering these three factors – empowerment, grievances, security – in our theory of change, the localized effects of mining on women's political participation result *a priori* ambiguous.

In this study, we shed light on the relationship between resource extraction and the gender gap in political participation at the local level. We develop a conceptual framework which describes the links between mining activities and changes in political participation, especially focusing on women. The framework builds on existing models of civic and political participation, and identifies the drivers most likely to be influenced by a resource shock. We then

proceed to empirically test the relationship between mining and the gender gap in political participation.

Our analysis relies on a dataset combining information from four rounds of the Afrobarometer survey and the Raw Materials Database (RMD) of SNL Metals and Mining by S&P. These two sets of data are matched using precise GPS point coordinates. In the first part of the analysis, we perform a difference-in-differences estimation using both spatial variation and temporal variation in mining activities. In the second part, we exploit time variation in international commodity prices, combined with data on mineral and metal deposits. Moreover, we employ four additional sets of (i) time-invariant geological data on global major mineral deposits from USGS¹, (ii) data on geological suitability of Africa for artisanal gold mining (Girard et al., 2021), (iii) data from ACLED on conflict and, (iv) migration data from Niva et al. (2023) to understand heterogeneity of the results.

The results of our analysis challenge findings from previous macro-level studies. We show that the gender gap in political participation narrows in proximity to active mines in four dimensions: (i) discussing politics, (ii) voting, (iii) attending community meetings, and (iv) accepting women as leaders. The narrowing of the gap is primarily driven by women's increased political participation near active mines, rather than a decrease in men's participation. The fifth dimension, protesting, is the only outcome that remains unaffected. The results are stable to varying treatment definitions, such as using ever operated mines or time variation stemming from international commodity prices. Moreover, the general patterns found are robust to different specifications, varying controls, fixed effects and clustering.

In an alternative specification, interacting international gold price and geological suitability for artisanal and small-scale (ASM) gold mining, we find that the intensification of ASM gold mining activities has no statistically significant effect on the gender gap in political participation. The lack of effects may stem from the intricate ways in which ASM interacts

¹The data can be retrieved from: <https://mrdata.usgs.gov/major-deposits/> (accessed July 28, 2023).

with local communities, often creating informal and less integrated settlements, or because the analysis relies on less variation due to the gold belts being large in size and interacted only with one commodity price: gold.

To further understand heterogeneity of the results, we categorize our data based on conflict and migration pressure. Using ACLED data, we categorize each enumeration area as low or high conflict based on the number of conflict events within 20 km recorded in the data, in the three years prior to the survey collection. Women in low conflict areas see a closing of the gender gap along the four dimensions. In high and very high conflict areas, we observe smaller effect sizes and statistically insignificant effects. The coefficient for protest is, in fact, negative although statistically insignificant in high conflict areas.

Using a novel dataset from [Niva et al. \(2023\)](#) we test if migration may be driving our results. Using data on communal (administrative level 3) data on migration in the three years prior to the Afrobarometer survey year, we classify areas (i) inward migration, (ii) outward migration, or (iii) net zero migration areas. In this analysis, we do not consider migration to be exogenous to the mining activities, rather we compare across areas experiencing the three levels of migration. Overall, migration does not seem to explain the effects on the first four dimensions of political participation².

Testing for different explanatory mechanisms, we find that increased labor force participation is key. We show that mining is positively associated with women's employment with a stronger effect for part-time work. The results suggest that, while mining predominantly offers part-time job opportunities to women, these could be sufficient to trigger a change in their political behaviours and attitudes.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature, while Section 3 presents the conceptual framework. Section 4 describes the data, Section 5

²The magnitudes and significance levels of the coefficients vary across the three levels, but all coefficients are economically significant and positive. Furthermore, we note that an area may, for example, have net no migration but still experience selective inward or outward migration, or intra-communal migration.

presents our empirical specification and Section 6 discusses the main findings and robustness checks. Section 7 tests a number of mechanisms before the concluding remarks in Section 8.

2 Localized effects of mining

The role of resource extraction as a driver of inequality started receiving attention with the work of Sachs and Werner (1995; 2001) on what became widely known as the ‘resource curse hypothesis’. The hypothesis holds that resource wealth hinders long-term growth through appreciation of exchange rates, de-industrialization, volatility, corruption and conflict (Cust & Poelhekke, 2015; van der Ploeg, 2011). Later studies have suggested that extraction has negative effects beyond economic performance, and that some of these effects disproportionately impact women. Ross (2008) showed, for instance, that women’s political exclusion in the Middle East can be explained through countries’ specialization in oil production, which crowds out female-dominated industries and reinforces patriarchal societal structures. Supporting this evidence, Awoa et al. (2022) found that resource wealth across countries is negatively correlated to female workforce participation, education and fertility, which result in depressed female political participation.

In recent years, macro-level findings on the relationship between resource extraction, growth and female political participation have been challenged by a growing body of micro-level literature. Studies have shown that mining activities can, at the local level, improve living standards (Aragón & Rud, 2013; Lippert, 2014; Loayza & Rigolini, 2016; Bazillier & Girard, 2020; Mamo et al., 2019) and the provision of public goods (Konte & Vincent, 2021). For women, the opening of a mining site has been found to trigger an important shift from agricultural jobs to more remunerative opportunities in the service sector (Benshaul-Tolonen, 2023; Kotsadam & Tolonen, 2016). In Zambia, these new opportunities have lead women to abandon the sex industry, with positive implications for their overall health (Wilson, 2012).

Regarding health and the environment, mining has been linked to a number of issues (e.g. heavy metal leakages), to which women are often more exposed (Corno & de Walque, 2012; Romero & Saavedra, 2019; von der Goltz & Barnwal, 2019). Recent studies have, however, brought a different perspective, showing that women living near mines experience improved healthcare access (Benshaul-Tolonen, 2023; Guimbeau et al., 2021) and lower infant mortality (Benshaul-Tolonen, 2019).

These findings add to new evidence pointing towards a positive impact of mining activities on gender norms and empowerment (Baum & Benshaul-Tolonen, 2021). Studies have found that, following the expansion of mining activities, women near mines are more likely to be involved in household decision-making (Guimbeau et al., 2021) and less likely to tolerate domestic violence (Benshaul-Tolonen, 2023; Guimbeau et al., 2021). The latter is a particularly important outcome, even if it does not automatically translate to a reduction of violence itself (Fourati et al., 2021; Kotsadam et al., 2017).

Overall, the literature on the localized effects of mining shows that, despite challenges, the sector can provide resources and opportunities for women, while also promoting change in traditional gender norms. While these factors may improve female political participation, no local-level study has yet tested this hypothesis. The present research aims to fill this gap by analyzing the impact of mining on gender differences in political participation. In doing so, it also aims to provide additional evidence on the drivers of political engagement across genders in low- and middle-income countries, as will be discussed in the next section.

2.1 Conceptual Framework

This study proposes a conceptual framework to delineate the mechanisms linking mining expansion to differences in political participation between men and women. Particularly, we focus on how resource extraction could affect female political empowerment. The framework draws from Downs' (1957) rational voting model and Gottlieb's (2014) gendered interpreta-

tion of it. In the model, the decision to participate in electoral systems is a function of the probability of voting leading to a beneficial result (p), the value of such result (B), and the costs of taking action (C):

$$E(V) = p(B) - C \quad (1)$$

Gender gaps in civic and political participation have been explained through the higher costs women face (C), in spite of having more to gain from a change in status quo (B). In fact, women are usually poorer in time and money, have less access to social and information networks, and experience discrimination in public spaces. We note that the value of the parameters are likely to change depending on the political activity women engage in.

Empirical studies that have analyzed the drivers of political participation emphasize the significance of socio-economic and cultural factors in shaping women's political (dis)empowerment (Bleck & Michelitch, 2018). Differences in education, formal employment, civic and family life are crucial to explain the inequalities in resources and opportunities that set women back in spaces of decision making. When resources cannot explain the observed gender gap in full, patriarchal norms are usually another contributing factor to the gender gap. Studies have found that gender norms not only prevent women from moving away from their traditionally marginal role in political spaces, but can even offset the benefits of them gaining access to more resources (Gottlieb, 2016). Several authors warn, however, that more evidence is needed to understand gender gaps in political participation in low- and middle-income countries (Isaksson et al., 2014).

Our framework (see Figure 1) breaks down explanatory channels between mining effects and outcomes. Among the many social and economic effects of mining, we identify six main ones: (i) changes in labor force participation, (ii) changes in household income, (iii) in-migration of workers, (iv) government transfers, (v) pollution, (vi) conflict and violence. These effects

generate two sets of outcomes that represent internal and external factors driving changes in resources and, therefore, political empowerment. Among the outcomes, there is also ‘grievances’ which captures dissatisfaction with mining and, thus, how much individuals could value political action.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework for Mining and Political Participation

First, it is important to consider the impact of mining expansion on local labor markets and, consequently, socio-economic resources (*internal factors*). Particularly relevant for women is workforce participation, as it may provide them with stronger bargaining power inside and

outside the household (Heath & Mobarak, 2015; Iversen & Rosenbluth, 2006, 2008; Jensen, 2012; Sanin, 2022), and mining has been shown to increase labor force participation³. At the same time, employment may impose stricter time constraint on people and especially women, who typically are also responsible for housework and care work.

Alongside labor markets, mining activities affect migration patterns, availability of public services, pollution and security⁴. In other words, the sector shapes the context (*external factors*) in which individuals make political decisions. The influx of workers, typically male, has two main consequences: (i) it facilitates the spread of sexually-transmitted diseases, and (ii) it skews local demographics⁵. A male-biased sex ratio is associated with women marrying younger and an increased likelihood of working inside the house (Grosjean & Khattar, 2019).

Pollution from mining can lead to long-lasting health damages and food insecurity. In contrast, health may not decrease if the increased pollution burden is offset by increases in income and health care access⁶.

Finally, resource-driven conflict and violence can deter people, especially women, from engaging in political activities⁷.

If they are exposed to more negative externalities, women can harbor stronger grievances while experiencing higher barriers to political participation. Overall, our conceptual framework highlights that mining effects on the gender gap in political participation is *a priori* ambiguous. This motivates the empirical analysis below.

³See Benschaul-Tolonen (2023); Guimbeau et al. (2021); Kotsadam et al. (2017); Aguilar-Gomez & Benschaul-Tolonen (2023).

⁴See Corno & de Walque (2012); Berman et al. (2017); von der Goltz & Barnwal (2019); Baum & Benschaul-Tolonen (2021); Konte & Vincent (2021)

⁵See Corno & de Walque (2012); Aguilar-Gomez & Benschaul-Tolonen (2023)

⁶See von der Goltz & Barnwal (2019); Benschaul-Tolonen (2019); Wegenast et al. (2019).

⁷See Berman et al. (2017); Fourati et al. (2021)

3 Data

The empirical analysis in this study relies on different sets of data, matched to one another by GPS coordinates. Throughout this section, we will proceed to describe the different identification strategies. The main dataset is composed of Afrobarometer survey data geo-referenced to information on mineral deposits, as reported in the Raw Materials Database (RMD) of SNL Metals and Mining by S&P ⁸. This dataset has been merged with additional sets of information on conflict events (ACLED data), and international commodity prices. To expand on our findings and for robustness analysis, the empirical strategy has been applied to a second dataset matching Afrobarometer survey data to information on mineral deposits sourced from different databases, including the Mineral Resource Data System (MDRS) by the United States Geological Survey (USGS) and the geological map of artisanal gold mining (AGM) suitability by Girard et al. (2021).

Matching. The main dataset was created through a two-steps process, following Konte and Vincent (2021). The process can be described as follows. First, using point GPS coordinates, each enumeration area in the Afrobarometer survey is matched to its closest mine. In a second step, each year of survey data collection is matched to the reference year for the last update on mine status. If the reference year does not have a direct correspondent among the Afrobarometer survey rounds, it is matched with the closest in time. In cases where data for enumeration area was missing, GPS coordinates for towns or district were used. Insights into sample composition by mine proximity are provided in Table 1.

Due to differences in the data structure across databases, the second dataset was created following a separate process. In the case of the USGS, Afrobarometer observations were matched to all mineral deposits located within a 20km radius. Then, information on said

⁸Standard & Poor's Global Market Intelligence

deposits (e.g. main mineral) was summarized. The dataset developed by Girard et al. (2021) for artisanal gold mining suitability is, instead, in grid form and comes in shapefile format. To identify the Afrobarometer observations located in areas suitable for artisanal gold mining (ASGM), their GPS coordinates were overlain the gridded map in QGIS. We created the dummy variable ‘asmgold’ taking value 1 if an Afrobarometer observation is located in an area which is suitable for artisanal gold mining, and 0 otherwise.

Table 1: Sample Composition across Databases

	Close to Mine		Far from Mine		Total
	Female	Male	Female	Male	
RMD	7,188	7,106	68,134	67,803	150,231
USGS	16,694	16,609	58,628	58,300	150,231
AGM	20,530	20,421	54,792	54,488	150,231

Note: In the case of RMD and USGS Databases, Afrobarometer observations are classified ‘close to a mine’ if they are located within a 20km radius, and ‘far from a mine’ if they are not. In the case of the dataset from Girard et al. (2022), an Afrobarometer observation is classified ‘close to a mine’ if its location overlaps with that of a geological bedrock suitable for artisanal gold mining, and ‘far from a mine’ otherwise.

Afrobarometer survey. Afrobarometer gathers large public surveys for 38 African countries and is a key source of information on people’s political and socio-economic characteristics. Our dataset includes four survey rounds for a total of over 60,000 respondents and a survey period between the year 2005 and 2015. For an overview of countries and survey rounds, see Table A2 in the Appendix. The Afrobarometer survey allows us to study five dimensions of political participation , namely (i) discussing politics, (ii) voting, (iii) attending community meetings,(iv) accepting women as leaders, (v) protesting. The dependent variables capturing these political behaviours and attitudes are operationalized from the survey questions listed in Table A1 of the Appendix.

The Afrobarometer surveys also allow us to construct variables for additional outcomes of

interest (such as gender attitudes), individual controls (such as age, urban/rural, religion, education) and potential mechanisms. It is important to note that certain questions, like those capturing gender norms, are only available for a subset of countries and rounds. To test possible mechanisms that could explain the relationship between mining and female political participation, we use survey questions regarding people's (i) employment, (ii) various resources (e.g. water and food security), (iii) trust towards different institutions, (iv) satisfaction levels with respects to service provision, living standards, crime and corruption. Additionally, we construct variables capturing the presence of different public goods and services.

Raw Minerals Database. In this study, we use three different mining datasets. The first one, included in our main dataset, is the Raw Materials Database (RMD). The RMD reports geo-location, name, status, commodity extracted and other information on 1417 mineral deposits across the African continent. In addition, the dataset provides information on the last year in which information on the status of the mine was collected. For an overview of the number of mines included in the RMD by their status and main mineral, see Table A3 and Table A4 of the Appendix. We visualized the geographical distribution of mineral deposits in Panel (A) of Figure 2 below, and compared it across the other datasets.

Table 2 describes the dataset geo-matching Afrobarometer survey data to information on mineral deposits reported in the RMD. The table summarizes baseline characteristics, as well as responses to questions related to political participation, for female and male respondents by proximity to an active or inactive mine. Proximity is defined through a 20km distance threshold. As shown in the table below, the sample remains equally split between men and women, regardless of their location. The last column reports the results of a t-test of the means in Column 3 and Column 7. The asterisks indicate when the means were found to be statistically different applying a 95 confidence interval.

Table 2: Sex-disaggregated Descriptive Statistics by Mine Proximity in RMD

	Far from Active Mine		Near Active Mine		Far from Inactive Mine		Near Inactive Mine		(9) T-test (3) = (7)
	(1) Female	(2) Male	(3) Female	(4) Male	(5) Female	(6) Male	(7) Female	(8) Male	
N	6,866	6,856	1,423	1,383	20,799	20,720	5,047	5,025	
Age	36.57	38.95	35.45	39.04	35.44	38.59	35.75	38.47	/
Urban	0.40	0.40	0.53	0.53	0.35	0.35	0.48	0.48	*
Employment status	0.27	0.37	0.30	0.39	0.30	0.41	0.31	0.42	*
Education of Respondent									*
No formal education	0.15	0.11	0.15	0.13	0.20	0.12	0.17	0.11	
Informal education	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.04	
Primary education	0.37	0.33	0.31	0.29	0.36	0.34	0.31	0.29	
Secondary education	0.36	0.40	0.41	0.42	0.31	0.36	0.35	0.39	
Post-secondary/University	0.10	0.13	0.16	0.14	0.08	0.13	0.12	0.17	
Discuss politics									*
Never	0.38	0.25	0.39	0.27	0.40	0.26	0.38	0.25	
Occasionally	0.46	0.49	0.45	0.48	0.45	0.46	0.45	0.46	
Frequently	0.16	0.26	0.16	0.25	0.15	0.28	0.17	0.29	
Community meeting	0.59	0.67	0.57	0.64	0.59	0.64	0.60	0.67	*
Voted National Election	0.73	0.77	0.73	0.76	0.74	0.79	0.75	0.78	*
Women leaders	0.39	0.45	0.52	0.50	0.36	0.41	0.47	0.49	*
Protest	0.09	0.12	0.12	0.15	0.08	0.12	0.09	0.13	*

Note: Respondents are classified as near a mine if they live within a 20km radius, far if they are between 20km and 100km. Column (9) reports the results of a t-test of the difference between the mean values of Column (3) and Column (7). Asterisk indicates a statistically significant differences, backslash indicates no difference.

United States Geological Survey. An alternative dataset used in our study is the Mineral Resource Data System (MRDS) of United States Geological Survey (USGS). The USGS-MRDS dataset is a collection of reports on metallic and nonmetallic mineral resources, providing extensive information (e.g. location, commodity, ownership) on 2752 deposits across the African continent. Table 3 describes the main minerals in the MRDS, and compares them with the RMD.

Artisanal Gold Mining. The novel dataset developed by Girard et al. (2021), instead, maps geological bedrocks suitable for artisanal gold mining (AGM) in Africa. The data evidences that about 18% of the continent is suitable for AGM.

Figure 2: Maps of Mineral Deposits and Migration Databases

Note: (A) Map of mineral and metal deposits. Only the main mineral/metal for each deposit is shown. Deposits are shown for countries included in the study only. Data from Raw Materials Database. (B) Map of mineral/metal deposits. Data from Mineral Resource Data System of the USGS. (C) Map of the geological bedrocks suitable for artisanal gold mining in Africa. Data from [Girard et al. \(2021\)](#). (D) Map for annual net migration. Net migration values are calculated across a 20 years period from 2000 to 2019. Data from [Niva et al. \(2023\)](#).

Migration. To further our analysis of potential mechanisms, we rely on the newly developed dataset by Niva et al. (2023) on world’s migration patterns between 2000 and 2019. The dataset provides information on annual net migration at multiple scales: regional and national (administrative level 0), provincial (administrative 1) and communal (administrative 2). Values for annual net migration are calculated by collecting, gap-filling, harmonizing and comparing national and sub-national level birth and death data. We visualize the dataset in Figure 2. In QGIS, we geo-matched Afrobarometer survey data to information on migration flows at the lowest administrative level for the enumeration area in which the observation is located. The migration data allows us to compare migration pressure between mining and non-mining areas, and to split Afrobarometer observations between (i) out-migration, (ii) in-migration and (iii) non-migration areas.

Table 3: Main Minerals across Databases

	Mineral 1	Mineral 2	Mineral 3	Mineral 4	Mineral 5	Other
<i>RMD</i>						
Mineral	Gold	Iron Ore	Diamonds	Uranium	Copper	
Share	34.80	10.13	8.70	7.43	6.36	32.58
<i>USGS</i>						
Mineral	Gold	Phosphorus	Copper	Manganese	Aluminum	
Share	19.25	12.41	5.62	4.90	4.74	53.08

Note: The table elaborates on information reported in the dataset geo-matching Afrobarometer observations to mineral deposits included in the RMD and USGS databases. The information reports the share of Afrobarometer observations close to each mineral for the five most frequent minerals, ranked in descending order. It is important to note that the total number of commodities reported in RMD is 31 versus 56 in USGS.

ACLED. The Armed Conflict & Event Data (ACLED) Project collects disaggregated data for all reported political violence and protest events around the world. To complete the analysis of potential mechanisms, this data was used to generate information on conflict in

mining areas. The process looked as follows. First, we exploited point GPS coordinates to match each Afrobarometer observation to all conflict events that had taken place within a 20km radius in the three years prior to the survey data collection. Information regarding these conflicts was then summarized in a set of continuous and dummy variables (e.g. total number of events), some of which are described in Table 4. Based on this information, Afrobarometer observations could be split between low, high and very high conflict areas for the purpose of our analysis.

Table 4: ACLED Conflict Events by Mine Proximity (RMD)

	Close to Mine	Far from Mine	Total
<i>Conflict</i>			
Incidence	11.14	11.93	11.85
N. of obs. exposed	7,300	56,208	63,508
Share of obs. exposed	51.07	41.35	/
<i>Protest</i>			
Incidence	11.36	10.93	10.98
N. of obs. exposed	5,154	35,790	40,944
Share of obs. exposed	70.06	63.67	/
<i>Riot</i>			
Incidence	4.90	5.35	5.29
N. of obs. exposed	4,874	34,090	38,964
Share of obs. exposed	66.77	60.65	/
<i>Violence against civilians</i>			
Incidence	3.56	8.15	7.62
N. of obs. exposed	4,613	37,608	38,964
Share of obs. exposed	63.19	66.91	/

Note: The table elaborates on information reported in the dataset geo-matching Afrobarometer survey data to ACLED data and information on mineral deposits contained in the RMD. In each panel, ‘incidence’ captures the total number of events that have taken place, within a 20km radius, in the three years prior each round of the Afrobarometer survey.

International commodity prices. Data on international commodity prices is provided by the

Primary Commodity Price System (PCPS) of the International Monetary Fund (IMF). The database reports price time series for numerous commodities, as well as indexes, for the period 1990-2023. For the purpose of our analysis, we created a continuous variable for the yearly price of each commodity averaging across reported monthly prices. Figure 3 reports the log price fluctuations for a subset of commodities and indexes across the years 1990-2023. Each round of Afrobarometer was matched to information on international commodity prices based on exact year.

Figure 3: Commodity Prices Time-Series

Note: Data sourced from the PCPS of the IMF. Values on the y-axis are reported in log scale.

4 Empirical Strategy

The empirical strategy employed in this study relies on a difference-in-differences approach, exploiting both geographic variation to identify the effects of proximity to a mine, and vari-

ation in mining activity to identify the effects of an active vs. inactive mine on the gender gap in political participation. Following Kotsadam and Tolonen (2016), our sample includes all individuals living within 100 km to a mine. The geographical variation is represented by the distance from a deposit, with a cut-off value set at 20km while the variation in mining activity is defined through the status of the mine.

As mentioned in the previous section, the Afrobarometer survey allows us to study five dimensions of political participation, which represent our dependent variables: (i) discussing politics, (ii) voting, (iii) attending community meetings, (iv) accepting women as leaders, (v) protesting. The first variable is coded as categorical, indicating how frequently the respondent participates in the activity: (i) never, (ii) occasionally, (iii) frequently. The others are coded as dummy variables, taking value 1 if the respondent engages in the activity, 0 otherwise. For a sample limited to individuals living in locations within 100 km from a mineral deposit, the baseline regression takes the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_{ilrt} = & \\
 & \beta_0 + \beta_1 Deposit_l(20km) \cdot Active_{lt} \cdot Female_i \\
 & + \beta_2 Deposit_l(20km) \cdot Active_{lt} \\
 & + \beta_3 Deposit_l + \beta_4 Female_i \\
 & + X_i + \delta_r + \theta_m + \gamma_t + \epsilon_{ilrt}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Where Y_{ilrt} is the political participation outcome of individual i , living in location l , region r and interviewed at time t . The variable $Female$ takes value 1 if the respondent is a woman and 0 if the respondent is a man. The variable $Deposit$ takes a value of 1 if there is a deposit within a 20 km range of a location l and 0 otherwise, regardless of whether mining activities are taking place or not. The variable $Deposit (20 km) \times Active$, instead, is an indicator of the deposit's industrial production status, which equals 1 for active mine and 0 otherwise.

In the survey, the vast majority of deposits (96%) were coded as either active or inactive⁹. The remaining 4% were categorized as undergoing maintenance, on hold, in rehabilitation, or under litigation. As these processes can take years, we consider the deposits as *de facto* inactive and coded them accordingly. Finally, the coefficient on the interaction term between *Female* and *Deposit (20 km) x Active* captures the effects of proximity to an active mine on political participation of women.

X_i includes additional control variables such as the age of the respondent in logs ($\text{age}(\ln)$), the respondent's religion, and her/his level of education. The variable for education is coded in five categories, namely (i) no education, (ii) informal education, (iii) primary education, (iv) secondary education and (v) post-secondary/University education. All the regressions include region, year and mineral fixed-effects. Standard errors are clustered at the mine level. Various robustness checks are performed varying clustering, combination of fixed-effects and the baseline distance from the mine (30km, 50km).

5 Results

5.1 Main results

The main results of our analysis are displayed in Table 5 Panel A, where men living further than 20km from a mineral deposit represent the base category. First, we compare men and women living far away from mining, and find the latter to be less likely to engage in any political activity, as well as less likely to perceive women as viable leaders. This is not surprising given that, as we said earlier, women have been traditionally excluded from politics and decision-making. Then, we look at the effects of proximity to a deposit, even if inactive. We see that the coefficient of 'Deposit' is positive for the first two dependent

⁹*Active* does not appear alone in the regression equation since there is no economic interpretation of being a non-mining area with active mining production.

variables and negative for the last three. This suggests that people living near mineral deposits are more likely, compared to those living far away, to discuss politics and vote, but less likely to participate in community meetings and protest, as well as less likely to accept women leaders.

The results change when exclusively considering active mines. First, we see that the coefficient of ‘Active Deposit’, which captures the effects of a mine being active, is opposite to that of ‘Deposit’ for all dependent variables, except ‘Community Meeting’. The comparison between individuals living close to inactive versus active deposits shows that the latter are less likely to discuss politics and vote, but more likely to protest and accept women leaders. Instead, little changes in terms of their likelihood of participating in community meetings. Once we disaggregate for gender, we find that the gap in political participation between men and women shrinks in proximity to active mines for all activities, except protesting. The effects are sizeable relative to the means: the gender gap in discussing politics shrinks by 18.4%, voting with 67%, attending community meetings with 28%. The gender gap in accepting women as leaders almost disappears (-95%). This is a result of women living near active deposits being more likely, compared to those living elsewhere, to engage in politics.

In contrast, we observe no change in the gender gap in protest participation. Previous research has found that protests are more common near mines ([Christensen, 2019](#))¹⁰; thus, this cannot be understood as a zero change in the likelihood of women protesting. Rather, men and women in mining communities are more likely to protest, but there is no change in the gender gap. We posit two main hypotheses why women are not protesting more despite having increased political participation: i) protests near mines are linked to violence which could deter women to partake ([Berman et al., 2017](#); [Fourati et al., 2021](#)); ii) protests near mines are linked to unionization ([Harvey, 2016](#)), and women are less likely unionized due to

¹⁰Mitigated by rising commodity prices and lack of communication in industry-community relations. Recent transparency initiatives such as the Extractive Industries and Transparency Initiative (EITI) reduces the likelihood of protests ([Christensen, 2019](#)).

their lower levels of employment as miners.

5.2 Mine life stages

Next, we modify the definition of ‘active’ deposit. In our baseline analysis, we categorized mines based on the variable ‘Status’ as reported in the RMD Database (see Table A3). For robustness, we switched instead to the variable ‘Stage’, indicating the level of mine development. Stages were summarized in four broad categories: (i) exploration, (ii) investment, (iii) production, and (iv) closing. We coded a new dummy ‘Operated’ to identify all mines that were active at any given point in time, as opposed to those that never were. The variable takes value 1 if the mine is classified as ‘active’ (based on status), ‘producing’ or ‘closed’ (based on stage). This allows us to compare ‘operated’ mines to those that are in their preparatory phases of exploration and investment. The results are displayed in Table 5 Panel B. While some estimates lose statistical significance, the direction remains the same. Interestingly, operated mines have a large significant effect on women’s attitudes towards female leadership. This may suggest that mining activities have long-lasting effects on gender norms which remain after operations cease¹¹.

5.3 International Mineral Prices

To gain further exogeneity in the empirical model due to concerns that the operative status of the mine is dependent on local characteristics, we perform a new model where we interact mineral deposits from the USGS with international commodity prices. We match the main mineral (m) in a deposit in the USGS database with the log price of that mineral (m) in year t . Thereby, we have temporal variation (from prices) and geographic variation (from deposit

¹¹We do not have enough statistical power to exclusively look at closed and suspended mines. For further insights into the long run effects from mine closures, please refer to (Aragon et al., 2015; Aguilar-Gomez & Benschaul-Tolonen, 2023; Maurer & Potlogea, 2021; Kotsadam & Tolonen, 2016).

Table 5: Main strategy, Operated Mines and Price Analysis

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Discuss Politics	Voting	Community Meeting	Women Leaders	Protest
PANEL A: ACTIVE MINES					
Deposit (20 km) x Active x Female	0.049* (0.027)	0.033* (0.018)	0.057* (0.033)	0.071*** (0.019)	0.003 (0.012)
Deposit (20 km) x Active	-0.081*** (0.023)	-0.031* (0.016)	0.001 (0.034)	-0.007 (0.017)	0.016 (0.012)
Deposit (20 km)	0.034*** (0.011)	0.005 (0.006)	-0.051*** (0.015)	-0.014** (0.007)	-0.011** (0.004)
Female	-0.219*** (0.006)	-0.011*** (0.003)	-0.156*** (0.007)	-0.083*** (0.004)	-0.032*** (0.002)
Observations	61916	59052	62171	53948	61226
PANEL B: OPERATED MINES					
Deposit (20 km) x Operated x Female	0.055** (0.023)	0.017 (0.016)	0.051* (0.028)	0.064*** (0.016)	0.000 (0.010)
Deposit (20 km) x Operated	-0.059*** (0.021)	-0.016 (0.014)	-0.019 (0.029)	-0.018 (0.015)	0.006 (0.011)
Deposit (20 km)	0.033*** (0.012)	0.005 (0.006)	-0.047*** (0.016)	-0.012 (0.007)	-0.010** (0.005)
Female	-0.219*** (0.006)	-0.012*** (0.004)	-0.159*** (0.007)	-0.083*** (0.004)	-0.031*** (0.002)
Observations	59812	57018	60063	52695	59156
PANEL C: USGS x PRICE					
USGS deposit (20 km) x Ln Price x Female	0.047** (0.022)	0.004 (0.012)	-0.009 (0.026)	0.096*** (0.024)	-0.003 (0.009)
USGS deposit (20 km) x Ln Price	-0.024 (0.041)	-0.029 (0.025)	0.046 (0.077)	-0.101*** (0.034)	-0.032* (0.017)
USGS deposit (20 km) x Female	-0.222** (0.112)	-0.030 (0.062)	0.053 (0.134)	-0.483*** (0.120)	0.003 (0.046)
Female x Ln Price	-0.046** (0.021)	0.002 (0.012)	0.009 (0.025)	-0.101*** (0.024)	0.008 (0.009)
USGS deposit (20 km)	0.123 (0.207)	0.160 (0.122)	-0.289 (0.385)	0.504*** (0.170)	0.164* (0.087)
Ln Price	0.024 (0.042)	0.026 (0.025)	-0.047 (0.075)	0.107*** (0.034)	0.031* (0.018)
Female	0.008 (0.104)	-0.026 (0.058)	-0.212* (0.124)	0.401*** (0.119)	-0.071* (0.043)
Observations	129816	123112	130327	103558	128224
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mineral FE	Panel A-B				

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. Panel A shows the main specification, clustering at the mine level. Panel B also clusters at mine level, while Panel C clusters at region level. In Panel B, the variable Operated takes value 1 if the mine is classified as 'active' (based on status), 'producing' or 'closed' (based on stage). USGS has no indicator for mine status, therefore the deposit variable is interacted with the price of the main mineral in the Afrobarometer survey year. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

location).¹² The advantage of this model is that it allows us to use an alternative dataset on

¹²Alternatively, we use a price index where we interact all mineral deposits with an international price index. Because this reduces the time variation in the data, we are not able to use year fixed effects. There

mines, USGS, which does not contain information on the status of the mine. Moreover, the dataset contains additional locations to the RMG database, including smaller deposits that may not be commercially viable mines for large mining companies.

The specification uses region and year fixed effects, but excludes mineral fixed effects since the new specification has mineral specific time trends interacted with the deposit.

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_{ilrt} = & \\
 & \beta_0 + \beta_1 USGSdeposit_{lm} \cdot LnPrice_{mt} \cdot Female_i \\
 & + \beta_2 USGSdeposit_{lm} \cdot LnPrice_{mt} \\
 & + \beta_3 USGSdeposit_{lm} \cdot Female_i \\
 & + \beta_4 USGSdeposit_{lm} + \beta_5 LnPrice_{mt} + \beta_6 Female_i \\
 & + \delta_r + \theta_e a + \epsilon_{ilrt}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Where Y_{ilrt} is the political participation outcome of individual i , living in enumeration area l , subnational region r and interviewed at time t . The variable $USGS_deposit$ takes value 1 if the respondent is located near a recorded metal or mineral deposit in the USGS dataset, and 0 otherwise. This variable is interacted with $LnPrice$, which captures the price of metals and minerals m , in year t . The main metal and mineral of each deposit is matched to the international commodity price of that particular metal and mineral in that year, t . The regression includes controls for age, education and religion. We add region and year fixed effects. We cluster standard errors at region level.

Table 5 Panel C shows that women living within 20 km from a USGS deposit are more likely to discuss politics and support women leaders in years of higher mineral prices.

results are available upon demand.

5.4 Heterogeneous Effects of Minerals

Mining operations can look very different depending on the target mineral. First, certain minerals are more likely to be extracted by large corporations while others, instead, have sizeable small-scale and artisanal mining sectors (ASM). This is the case, for instance, of gold. ASM is typically more labor-intensive¹³ and, for this reason, has been shown to generate more local spillovers than industrial mining (Bazillier & Girard, 2020). Women are also heavily involved in ASM (Jenkins, 2014; Benschaul-Tolonen, 2019; Zolnikov, 2020). At the same time, the production technology employed influences the effects that mines have on health and the environment. Artisanal gold mining is particularly problematic as the frequent use of mercury poses serious health risks, especially to women and infants (Gonzalez et al., 2019; Nyanza et al., 2019).

Broadly speaking, studies have shown that mining is tied to conflict and violence (Berman et al., 2017; Fourati et al., 2021), although the associations depend on how capital intensive mines are and the investment response (Blair et al., 2021). Certain minerals are more strongly linked to security issues than others. Notably, this has been the case of diamond mining with its infamous connections to civil conflict in several African countries. Some studies argue that characteristics of minerals like concealability and ‘lootability’ are strong predictors of conflict events (Lujala, 2009). Others, instead, have shown that value and bulkiness can also play an important role (Berman et al., 2017). We test for heterogeneous effects of minerals on the gender gap in political participation, and report the main results in Figure 4.

¹³The labor intensity of large-scale mines also varies, especially across minerals, engendering different impacts on local labor demand (Pelzl & Poelhekke, 2021). While we have data on minerals, and a separate dataset for ASM activities, we cannot test if heterogeneity along labor-capital intensity within large-scale mines drive our results.

Figure 4: Coefficient Plots by Mineral

Note: Clustered standard errors. Clustering at mine level. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. Fixed effects include region and year.

5.5 Heterogeneous Effects of Conflicts

Many African countries have recently experienced conflict, some of which are related to extractive industries (Berman et al., 2017). Conflict, as well as post-conflict, may also have direct influence on women’s political participation. In fact, a cross-country panel data analysis of African countries found that the end of long lasting major conflicts led to a boost in the share of women legislators (Hughes & Tripp, 2015), possibly indicating a catching up effect from depressed levels of participation or the socially disruptive effects of conflict on gender norms.

To explore how conflict may influence our estimates of extractive industries of female

political participation, we combine our dataset with the ACLED data on conflict and violent events. This allows us to compare the effects of proximity to a mine on the gender gap in political participation across low, high and very high conflict areas¹⁴.

Each Afrobarometer observation was matched to all conflict events that happened within a 20km distance in the three years prior surveying. Observations are split between low and high conflict areas using the median of the distribution of conflicts (which is 1 event) in the last three years as the cut-off value. Areas with the highest number of conflicts (“Very High Conflict”) represent, instead, the top quintile of the distribution.

Table 6 presents the results of our baseline regression for low, high and very high conflict areas. Conflict events include (i) violence against civilians, (ii) battles, (iii) protests, (iv) riots, (v) strategic developments and (vi) explosions/remote violence. As a robustness check, in Table A7 we perform the same analysis excluding protests from conflict events, since participation in protests is one of our outcome variables. Results are not substantially affected.

As shown in Table 6, proximity to mines has a stronger influence on the gender gap in political participation in low conflict settings. The interpretation is that in less conflict-prone areas, mining activities make men and women behave more similarly in terms of political participation.

Although not significant, we observe that the coefficient of our main interaction term turns negative but remains insignificant for protests when considering high conflict areas (Panel B). This finding seems to support our hypothesis on why the gender gap in protests does not shrink like other dimensions of political participation. It may be that women are less likely to engage in an activity that may expose them to violence. Results do not change substantially when looking exclusively at observations in extreme conflict areas (Panel C).

¹⁴We do not explore if mining causes conflicts.

Table 6: Low vs High Conflict Areas

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Discuss politics	Voting	Community Meeting	Women Leaders	Protest
PANEL A: LOW CONFLICT					
Deposit (20 km) x Active x Female	0.040 (0.036)	0.114*** (0.024)	0.052** (0.024)	0.078* (0.042)	0.020 (0.016)
Deposit (20 km) x Active	-0.057* (0.030)	-0.032 (0.021)	-0.041* (0.021)	-0.072* (0.041)	-0.017 (0.015)
Deposit (20 km)	0.024* (0.013)	-0.001 (0.008)	-0.001 (0.007)	-0.023 (0.017)	-0.004 (0.005)
Female	-0.217*** (0.007)	-0.078*** (0.005)	-0.014*** (0.004)	-0.159*** (0.008)	-0.029*** (0.003)
Observations	40339	34895	38630	40573	39841
PANEL B: HIGH CONFLICT					
Deposit (20 km) x Active x Female	0.052 (0.038)	0.011 (0.028)	0.000 (0.029)	0.027 (0.053)	-0.022 (0.019)
Deposit (20 km) x Active	-0.089** (0.036)	0.015 (0.027)	-0.012 (0.025)	0.060 (0.062)	0.055*** (0.020)
Deposit (20 km)	0.033* (0.017)	-0.038*** (0.012)	0.026** (0.011)	-0.049* (0.025)	-0.020*** (0.007)
Female	-0.229*** (0.011)	-0.084*** (0.007)	-0.008 (0.006)	-0.150*** (0.012)	-0.040*** (0.004)
Observations	21567	19045	20411	21588	21372
PANEL C: VERY HIGH CONFLICT					
Deposit (20 km) x Active x Female	0.061 (0.048)	-0.005 (0.036)	-0.014 (0.040)	0.023 (0.062)	-0.023 (0.024)
Deposit (20 km) x Active	-0.086* (0.048)	0.049 (0.037)	-0.013 (0.039)	0.024 (0.087)	0.048 (0.030)
Deposit (20 km)	0.035 (0.024)	-0.054*** (0.015)	0.040** (0.017)	-0.007 (0.035)	-0.018 (0.011)
Female	-0.226*** (0.014)	-0.083*** (0.009)	-0.011 (0.008)	-0.161*** (0.016)	-0.041*** (0.006)
Observations	12073	10658	11365	12070	11968
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mineral FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. Clustering at mine level. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Observations are matched to conflict events within 20km distance that happened in the three years prior survey. Low conflict (A) is defined below the median of the distribution of conflicts (1 event in the last three years) and high conflict (B) is defined above the median. Very high conflict (C) is defined as at the highest quintile of violence (more than 7 conflicts in the last three years).

5.6 Suitability for Artisanal Gold Mining

Gold mining is prevalent across the African continent, and the production methods range from large-scale mining (often reliant on foreign direct investment and multinational companies) to artisanal and small-scale mining (ASM), where the extraction is labor intensive with rudimentary technology, and sometimes illegal. ASM has attracted women to gold mining

camps across the African continent to gain employment opportunities and personal freedom (Werthmann, 2009; Brottem & Ba, 2019), and higher bargaining power in the household (Arthur-Holmes & Busia, 2020; Adam et al., 2022). At the same time, some studies highlight the risks that such women face, including reputation damage due to perceptions of sex work (Werthmann, 2009), cultural marginalization and lack of legal rights (Arthur-Holmes & Abrefa Busia, 2021).

Few studies have been able to quantitatively assess the different effects of large-scale and small-scale mining. One exception is Bazillier and Girard (2020) who evidenced the heterogeneous effects of industrial versus artisanal mining on consumption. To further explore this heterogeneity on outcomes related to political participation, we use a novel dataset by Girard et al. (2021) on artisanal gold mining suitability and interact it with the international gold price.

Applying a difference-in-differences approach, we exploit both spatial and temporal variation to identify the effects of changes in the opportunity for artisanal gold mining activities on the gender gap in political participation. The time-invariant geographic data on gold belts comes from Girard et al. (2021). The baseline regression is specified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_{ilrt} = & \\
 & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Goldbelt}_l \cdot \text{Gold_Price}_t \cdot \text{Female}_i \\
 & + \beta_2 \text{Goldbelt}_l \cdot \text{Gold_Price}_t \\
 & + \beta_3 \text{Goldbelt}_l \cdot \text{Female}_i \\
 & + \beta_4 \text{Gold_Price}_t \cdot \text{Female}_i \\
 & + \beta_5 \text{Goldbelt}_l + \beta_6 \text{Gold_Price}_t + \beta_7 \text{Female}_i \\
 & + \delta_r + \theta_l + \epsilon_{ilrt}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Where Y is the political participation outcome of individual i, living in location l, subnational region r and interviewed at time t. The variable *Goldbelt* takes value 1 if the respondent

is located in an area suitable for artisanal gold mining (ASM) and 0 otherwise. This variable is interacted with *Gold_Price*, which captures the price of gold in year t . The regression includes controls for age, education and religion. We add region fixed effects. We cluster standard errors at the regional level.

Because geological bedrocks are large, we have less spatial variation than in the previous empirical analysis, and the temporal variation comes from just one price vector (gold price) in Panel A, or a gold boom indicator (years 2009-2014) in Panel B. The results in Table 7 show that the effect of artisanal gold mining on political participation is negligible in magnitude and, for most outcomes, statistically insignificant. We do observe an increase in the likelihood of women in gold mining areas to report having voted in the last election.

6 Robustness

6.1 Sensitivity analysis of main results

We tested the robustness of our results by varying different aspects of our main specification. Table 8 shows the results of these tests for our main coefficient of interest. As anticipated in our previous section, estimates are robust to varying cut-off values and clustering. Through robustness checks, we first show that proximity is a key factor. When we increase the cut-off distance from a mine, effects drop substantially. With a cut off value set bigger than 30km, estimates also lose all significance. In addition to cut-off values, Table 8 shows the result of changing clustering strategy to enumeration area level and regional level, as opposed to mine level. The conclusion from our analysis does not change.

We investigated whether our estimates are also robust to different combinations of fixed effects. The results of this robustness check are displayed for key coefficients in Figure 5. To see results for all coefficients, see Table A4 of the Appendix. In Figure 5, we add the fixed effects (i) region-year, (ii) mineral, (iii) mine, (iv) enumeration area, mentioned. The last

Table 7: Artisanal Gold Mining Suitability interacted with Gold Price and Gold Boom

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Discuss Politics	Voting	Community Meeting	Women Leaders	Protest
PANEL A: GOLD BELT X LOG GOLD PRICE					
Goldbelt x Log Gold Price x Female	0.025 (0.023)	0.025* (0.015)	-0.023 (0.030)	-0.024 (0.023)	0.012 (0.012)
Goldbelt x Log Gold Price	-0.058** (0.029)	-0.039** (0.018)	0.041 (0.061)	0.023 (0.030)	0.015 (0.015)
Goldbelt x Female	-0.178 (0.164)	-0.186* (0.102)	0.135 (0.213)	0.194 (0.163)	-0.078 (0.081)
Log Gold Price x Female	-0.037*** (0.014)	-0.005 (0.008)	-0.009 (0.018)	-0.131*** (0.020)	0.013* (0.007)
Goldbelt	0.412** (0.201)	0.281** (0.127)	-0.302 (0.430)	-0.197 (0.218)	-0.106 (0.110)
Log Gold Price	-0.020 (0.019)	0.066*** (0.011)	-0.051 (0.036)	-0.335*** (0.020)	-0.058*** (0.010)
Female	0.044 (0.098)	0.018 (0.059)	-0.094 (0.123)	0.826*** (0.143)	-0.124** (0.049)
PANEL B: GOLD BELT X GOLD BOOM INDICATOR					
Goldbelt x Gold boom x Female	-0.004 (0.018)	0.018* (0.011)	-0.028 (0.020)	-0.016 (0.023)	-0.003 (0.008)
Goldbelt x Gold boom	-0.031 (0.022)	-0.025** (0.010)	-0.014 (0.040)	0.038 (0.044)	0.012 (0.012)
Goldbelt x Female	-0.002 (0.016)	-0.018* (0.009)	-0.010 (0.015)	0.032 (0.020)	0.006 (0.006)
Gold boom x Female	-0.028*** (0.010)	-0.000 (0.006)	0.004 (0.014)	-0.056*** (0.017)	0.012** (0.005)
Goldbelt	0.021 (0.018)	0.023*** (0.009)	-0.010 (0.028)	-0.061 (0.038)	-0.005 (0.009)
Gold boom	0.018 (0.015)	0.053*** (0.007)	-0.044** (0.021)	-0.197*** (0.022)	-0.044*** (0.007)
Female	-0.199*** (0.008)	-0.017*** (0.005)	-0.163*** (0.010)	-0.067*** (0.014)	-0.041*** (0.004)
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	131154	124437	131667	104235	129539

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. Clustering at region level. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. The dummy variable 'goldboom' takes value 1 for years between 2009-2014 and 0 otherwise. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

graph, thus presents the results for the full set of fixed effects. As shown below, adding fixed effects improves the precision of our estimates but the results are not affected by different specifications.

Table 8: Robustness Checks: Cut-off Values & Clustering

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Discuss politics	Voting	Community Meeting	Women leaders	Protest
CUT-OFF VALUES					
<i>PANEL A: Cut-off 30km</i>					
Deposit (30 km) x Active x Female	0.020 (0.022)	0.023 (0.014)	0.056** (0.027)	0.034** (0.015)	-0.002 (0.009)
<i>PANEL B: Cut-off 50km</i>					
Deposit (50 km) x Active x Female	0.023 (0.017)	0.002 (0.011)	0.029 (0.021)	0.012 (0.012)	-0.001 (0.007)
CLUSTERING					
<i>PANEL C: ENUMERATION AREA LEVEL</i>					
Deposit (20 km) x Active x Female	0.047* (0.026)	0.031* (0.019)	0.056* (0.033)	0.069*** (0.019)	0.002 (0.012)
<i>PANEL D: REGION LEVEL</i>					
Deposit (20 km) x Active x Female	0.047* (0.025)	0.031* (0.016)	0.056** (0.028)	0.069*** (0.024)	0.002 (0.013)
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mineral FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	61916	59052	62171	53948	61226

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. Clustering at mine level, for Panel A & B of section "Cut-off Values". All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

7 Mechanisms

7.1 Migration

One factor that could be driving our results and, thus, biasing our analysis is inward and outward migration in mining communities. We explore this possibility using the dataset developed by Niva et al. (2023), which provides information on annual net migration at the regional, provincial and communal level across the African continent. Our baseline analysis is replicated on a sample split which distinguishes enumeration areas based on the direction and intensity of migration flows during the three years prior to surveying: (i) in-migration areas, (ii) out-migration areas, and (iii) zero migration areas. The level and directionality of migration may be a direct effect of mining. Thereby, this categorization is not exogenous to

Figure 5: Robustness Checks: Fixed Effects

Note: All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. Clustering is at the mine level. The fixed effects are added one by one. The last graph contains all four fixed effects.

the treatment status. Table 9 presents the results.

Overall, the effects of proximity to an active mine on the gender gap in political participation remain consistent across different levels of migration exposure. All coefficients for the gender gap in mining communities are positive, although not all are statistically significant. In particular, women in active mining communities have stronger beliefs in women leaders, across all migration levels. Interestingly, however, women are found to be more likely to protest near active mines when exposed to inward migration, compared to outward or zero migration which could be driven by selective inward migration of women who are protest-prone. We cannot test this hypothesis further.

Table 9: Migration

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Discuss Politics	Voting	Community Meeting	Women Leaders	Protest
PANEL A: NET IN-MIGRATION					
Deposit (20 km) x Active x Female	0.022 (0.037)	0.019 (0.028)	0.052 (0.047)	0.044* (0.026)	0.036* (0.018)
Deposit (20 km) x Active	-0.078** (0.034)	-0.002 (0.024)	-0.003 (0.052)	0.026 (0.023)	0.002 (0.017)
Deposit (20 km)	0.044** (0.019)	0.001 (0.010)	-0.043 (0.026)	-0.035*** (0.012)	-0.019*** (0.007)
Female	-0.211*** (0.010)	-0.014** (0.006)	-0.150*** (0.011)	-0.082*** (0.006)	-0.037*** (0.004)
Observations	24289	23087	24379	20385	24041
PANEL B: NET OUT-MIGRATION					
Deposit (20 km) x Active x Female	0.070 (0.046)	0.057** (0.026)	0.046 (0.053)	0.089*** (0.029)	-0.031* (0.016)
Deposit (20 km) x Active	-0.084** (0.034)	-0.045* (0.025)	0.001 (0.049)	-0.045* (0.026)	0.028 (0.019)
Deposit (20 km)	0.021 (0.014)	0.004 (0.008)	-0.040** (0.019)	-0.002 (0.009)	-0.009 (0.006)
Female	-0.224*** (0.008)	-0.013*** (0.005)	-0.156*** (0.009)	-0.088*** (0.006)	-0.025*** (0.003)
Observations	32891	31379	33044	29326	32501
PANEL C: NET NO MIGRATION					
Deposit (20 km) x Active x Female	0.136* (0.082)	0.024 (0.067)	0.164 (0.103)	0.141** (0.066)	-0.006 (0.049)
Deposit (20 km) x Active	-0.236*** (0.089)	-0.093* (0.055)	-0.346*** (0.107)	-0.101** (0.049)	0.012 (0.069)
Deposit (20 km)	0.028 (0.054)	0.020 (0.037)	-0.021 (0.058)	0.012 (0.029)	-0.023 (0.031)
Female	-0.235*** (0.023)	0.004 (0.013)	-0.168*** (0.028)	-0.042** (0.019)	-0.066*** (0.010)
Observations	3673	3561	3684	3223	3633
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mineral FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. Clustering at mine level. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Observations are matched to information on migration flows at the administrative level 2 (communal). Areas are divided between those which in the three years prior surveying experienced (on average) inward migration (A), outward migration (B), and no migration flows (C).

7.2 Female employment

The conceptual framework outlined in Section 3 allows us to hypothesize different explanatory mechanisms for the effects we observe. Using Afrobarometer data, we can test the following

(i) changes in female labor force participation, (ii) government transfers, (iii) grievances, (iv) social tensions, (v) changes in other resources.

First, we investigate changes in female labor force participation near active mining deposits. The underlying idea is that mining could open up new employment opportunities for women, thus providing them with access to resources that are positively associated with political participation (Iversen & Rosenbluth, 2008; Bleck & Michelitch, 2018; Heath & Mobarak, 2015; Jensen, 2012; Baum & Benschaul-Tolonen, 2021; Sanin, 2022). Table 10 shows the results of our analysis. In general, there seem to be less employment opportunities - and especially full-time ones - near active deposits. Disaggregating by gender, we find however that women living in mining communities are more likely to have a part-time job. This can be explained by evidence showing that mine opening prompts women to move out of agriculture and into more remunerative service sector jobs that, according to qualitative evidence, often look like selling items, cooking, cleaning, driving (Jenkins, 2014; Kotsadam & Tolonen, 2016). These jobs are more likely to be part-time, compared to agricultural jobs. If the new part-time job opportunities brought by mining (directly or indirectly) provide women with higher wages or more social connections than those previously held, the employment channel could explain why gender gaps in political participation narrow near active deposits. Increasing direct employment of women as miners has also been linked to increasing political participation and the aspiration of women political leaders (Evans, 2016).

7.3 Gender attitudes

The expansion in mining in Africa affects gender roles, as captured by changes in attitudes towards domestic violence, labor force participation and access to healthcare (Benschaul-Tolonen, 2019). Here, we complement our main analysis by looking into different dimensions of gender norms and how they differ between men and women living close to active mines. In particular, we focus on a sub-set of questions in the Afrobarometer survey. The first question

Table 10: Female Employment Mechanism

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Employed	Employed Part-time	Employed Part-time	Employed Full-time	Employed Full-time
Deposit (20 km) x Active x Female	0.021 (0.017)	0.029** (0.012)	0.036** (0.015)	-0.008 (0.016)	-0.001 (0.017)
Deposit (20 km) x Active	-0.041** (0.019)	-0.009 (0.010)	-0.022 (0.014)	-0.032* (0.017)	-0.038** (0.019)
Deposit (20 km)	0.005 (0.008)	-0.006 (0.005)	-0.005 (0.006)	0.011 (0.007)	0.007 (0.008)
Female	-0.081*** (0.004)	-0.030*** (0.003)	-0.050*** (0.003)	-0.051*** (0.003)	-0.065*** (0.003)
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mineral FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	62307	62307	47944	62307	55108

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. Clustering at mine level. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Coefficients are omitted because of collinearity.

asks which statement is closest to the respondent’s view: (i) women should have equal rights versus (ii) women should remain subject to traditional laws and customs. The second question asks how much, when funding for school is limited, respondents would prioritize (i) boys versus (ii) children with greatest ability to learn. The last three questions ask how often respondents believe women are treated equally by (i) traditional leaders, (ii) police and courts, (iii) employers. As questions are not included for all countries in all rounds, we deal with a smaller sample of observations.

Table 11 shows the results for our analysis. Compared to men, women living far away from mining deposits are more likely to agree with equal rights of men and women, and perceive that women are treated equally by traditional leaders, police and courts and by employers. In proximity of mines, we only note one statistically significant change: women in mining communities are more likely to perceive that women are always or often being treated equally to men by employers. The effect is large: a 8.7 percentage point increase in the likelihood; a three time increase from the female-male indicator variable. This is interesting given the mining sector’s traditional male bias, and may further point to the power of employment to empower women.

Table 11: Gender Norms

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Equal Rights	Education Priority	Treated Trad. Leaders	Treated Police	Treated Employers
Deposit (20km) x Active x Female	0.018 (0.031)	-0.006 (0.036)	0.057 (0.053)	0.003 (0.040)	0.087** (0.038)
Deposit (20km) x Active	0.013 (0.029)	-0.036 (0.028)	0.014 (0.040)	0.033 (0.037)	0.014 (0.038)
Deposit (20km)	-0.000 (0.009)	0.009 (0.009)	0.010 (0.014)	0.025* (0.014)	0.003 (0.013)
Female	0.061*** (0.006)	-0.038*** (0.005)	0.058*** (0.006)	0.034*** (0.006)	0.029*** (0.007)
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mineral FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	22273	19591	21541	21316	20857

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. Clustering at mine level. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. The outcome variables are: (i) women should have equal rights (1) versus women should remain subject to traditional laws and customs (0), (ii) when funding for school are limited, respondents would prioritize boys (1) versus children with greatest ability to learn (0); how often respondents believe women are treated equally by (iii) traditional leaders, (iv) police and courts, (v) employers. Responses are coded (1) if always or often, and (0) if never or rarely. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

7.4 Access to resources

There are multifaceted ways in which mining can affect women's access to resources. The expansion of the sector may have effects on water and food insecurity (Wegenast & Beck, 2020), as well as access to healthcare (Guimbeau et al., 2021; Benshaul-Tolonen, 2023; Rhee et al., 2018) and cash availability. There are two reasons why this may affect the gender gap in political participation: (i) access to resources varies with gender, (ii) women and men exhibit different policy preferences for resource access (Gottlieb et al., 2018).

Table 12 reports the effects of proximity to mining on perceptions of food security, water security, access to healthcare, cash availability, a general poverty index and subjective perceptions of their living conditions compared to others. Here, we observe that the positive relationship between mining and access to healthcare (government transfer/public good provision) aligns with the existing literature (Benshaul-Tolonen, 2023; Guimbeau et al., 2021). The estimates are, however, statistically insignificant. The only significant estimate we find is the one for the dependent variable 'Water Security', suggesting that women near active mines express higher satisfaction with their water security.

Table 12: Resources Mechanism

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	Food Security	Water Security	Access Healthcare	Cash Availability	Poverty Index	Liv. Cond. Comp. to Others
Deposit (20km) x Activex Female	-0.006 (0.041)	0.096** (0.044)	0.075 (0.046)	-0.023 (0.047)	0.025 (0.028)	0.030 (0.032)
Deposit (20km) x Active	0.057 (0.044)	-0.031 (0.052)	0.034 (0.046)	-0.001 (0.053)	0.019 (0.032)	-0.019 (0.031)
Deposit (20km)	-0.035 (0.024)	-0.082*** (0.028)	-0.066*** (0.023)	-0.101*** (0.027)	-0.059*** (0.018)	0.013 (0.013)
Female	0.016* (0.008)	-0.040*** (0.009)	-0.037*** (0.009)	-0.003 (0.009)	-0.006 (0.005)	0.010 (0.007)
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mineral FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	62418	62420	62232	62266	61699	60901

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. Clustering at mine level. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

7.5 Satisfaction and Trust

Table 13 and Table 14 investigate the effects of mining proximity on satisfaction levels and trust in formal institutions. This allows us to test the hypothesis that our results are driven by grievances and/or social cohesion mechanisms.

Table 13 analyses the satisfaction levels of people living in proximity of mines. The analysis focuses on satisfaction towards how the government is handling living standards, health and education services, infrastructure, crime and corruption. Overall, the direction of the relationship between mining and satisfaction is positive for both men and women. Particularly, women seem to be more likely to be satisfied with how the government handles crime in proximity of active deposits. This is an interesting finding, especially in juxtaposition with what was highlighted in the previous paragraph, namely that women in mining communities are more likely to distrust the police. In general, the results align with existing literature showing that increases in mineral wealth reduce criminality (Axbard et al., 2021).

Table 14 shows that there is a positive, albeit insignificant, relationship between mining and trust towards institutions, but not towards others. Disaggregating by sex, the opposite is true. Women near active deposits are more likely to trust others and less likely to trust institutions. It's worth noting that only the estimates for the coefficients 'Tax Officials' and

‘Police’ are statistically significant.

Overall, we find no clear and robust impacts on satisfaction with living standards, public service provision or trust in local and national government that likely drive our results in women’s political participation.

Table 13: Satisfaction Mechanism

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Living Standards	Health & Education	Infrastructure	Crime	Corruption
Deposit (20 km) x Active x Female	0.010 (0.035)	0.015 (0.036)	0.038 (0.037)	0.071* (0.037)	0.017 (0.039)
Deposit (20 km) x Active	-0.003 (0.040)	0.070* (0.041)	0.037 (0.047)	0.009 (0.038)	0.067* (0.039)
Deposit (20 km)	-0.036* (0.020)	-0.022 (0.018)	0.016 (0.021)	-0.060*** (0.017)	-0.042** (0.018)
Female	-0.005 (0.007)	0.009 (0.007)	0.009 (0.007)	-0.022*** (0.007)	0.006 (0.007)
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mineral FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	61525	61571	61468	60595	58168

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. Clustering at mine level. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Table 14: Trust Mechanism

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	Others	Parliament	Ruling Party	Tax Officials	Local Council	Police	Courts
Deposit (20 km) x Active x Female	0.052 (0.084)	-0.021 (0.050)	-0.003 (0.046)	-0.133** (0.055)	-0.037 (0.046)	-0.089** (0.042)	-0.065 (0.040)
Deposit (20 km) x Active	-0.089 (0.077)	0.048 (0.041)	0.076* (0.044)	0.051 (0.051)	0.008 (0.041)	0.029 (0.043)	-0.031 (0.036)
Deposit (20 km)	0.012 (0.020)	-0.084*** (0.019)	-0.097*** (0.020)	-0.042* (0.021)	-0.059*** (0.017)	-0.056*** (0.020)	-0.054*** (0.017)
Female	-0.066*** (0.010)	-0.004 (0.008)	0.001 (0.009)	0.001 (0.010)	0.011 (0.008)	-0.008 (0.008)	0.002 (0.008)
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mineral FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	30622	59275	58823	41107	58836	61332	59714

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. Clustering at the mine level. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

8 Conclusion

Despite efforts being made towards closing the gender gap in political participation, significant inequalities persist between men and women. This is particularly true in the African continent. Macro-level studies have explained this phenomenon through the expansion of extractive industries, via worsening employment, education and fertility rates for women (Ross, 2008; Awoa et al., 2022). While the described mechanisms have been challenged by micro-level evidence, we analyzed the localized effects of mining activities on the gender gap in political participation. This is the gap that our research set out to fill. Our study contributes to the literature on the localized effects of natural resource extraction, and to the literature on natural resource driven economic development and female empowerment.

The empirical strategy employed in this study is structured in two parts. First, we perform a difference-in-differences estimation, exploiting geographic variation and variation in mining activity. This analysis relies on a comprehensive dataset geo-matching four rounds of Afrobarometer survey to information on mineral deposits contained in the RMD Database of SNL Metals and Mining by S&P. In a second step, we perform a difference-in-differences estimation, exploiting geographic and exogenous temporal variation stemming from international commodity prices. For this part of the analysis, we employ two additional datasets: USGS and a dataset on the geological suitability for artisanal gold mining (Girard et al., 2021).

The results of our analysis show that the gender gap in political participation narrows in proximity of mining activities. We find that the narrowing of the gap is primarily driven by women who, near active mines, are more likely to (i) discuss politics, (ii) vote, (iii) participate in community meetings, and (iv) accept women as leaders. Protesting is the only dimension, out of the five we examine, that remains unaffected. In general, findings are robust to different specifications, varying controls, fixed effects and clustering.

Expanding on our analysis, we explore differences in our results across areas with varying degrees of conflict exposure. We find that women near active mines in low-conflict areas are more politically active than those in high-conflict ones. Interestingly, the coefficient for protest (although statistically insignificant) turns negative in high- and very high-conflict areas. This result suggests that women may be more reluctant to engage in political activities with a higher chance of turning violent. Finally, we find that the effects of artisanal mining on the gender gap in political participation are negligible and statistically insignificant.

Among potential explanatory mechanisms, labor force participation stands out as the most important one. We find that women's employment, and specifically part-time work, increases near active mines. The results indicate that although mining primarily provides women with part-time employment opportunities, the impact of these opportunities may be significant enough to influence shifts in their political behaviors and attitudes. Women in mining communities are 3 times more likely to report that women are always or often treated equally to men by employers. In contrast, we find few impacts on gender norms, resource availability, and satisfaction of public services that could explain our results. We do find, however largely insignificant, reduced level of trust in government bodies such as Parliament, tax officials and police.

It has been conjectured that extractive industries, including mining activities, disempower women through reducing access to jobs, increasing the gender wage gap, and affecting women's access to resources, health and environmental amenities. It was also hypothesized that extractive industries will reduce women's political influence and organization.

The results from our pan-African, multi-mineral, study using several identification strategies show the opposite. We consistently find increases in women's political participation, alongside improvements in employment, perceptions on how fairly women are treated by employers, water security, and satisfaction with local crime levels. We find no evidence of disempowerment of women, or deterioration in their livelihoods. Two notable exceptions:

women do not increase their participation in protests (only in in-ward migration areas), and even decrease protest participation in high conflict and net outward migration areas. Moreover, women report lower trust in some government organization, which could stem from a deterioration in trustworthiness or, indeed, an increased political awareness.

High levels of conflict has a dampening effect on women's political empowerment. Therefore, policy makers ought to carefully consider current levels of conflict, and risk of conflict intensification, when predicting the gender effects of mining activities.

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Appendix A Summary Tables

Table A1: Afrobarometer Survey Questions and N. of Countries per Round asked

Survey Question	R3	R4	R5	R6
When you get together with your friends or family, would you say you discuss political matters?	18	20	33	30
Please tell me whether you, personally, have attended a community meeting	18	20	33	30
Did you vote in the most recent national elections?	18	20	33	29
Are you OK with women being leaders?	18		33	29
Please tell me whether you, personally, have participated in a demonstration or protest march	18	20	33	29

Note: The table reports the number of countries per Afrobarometer round where the questions were asked. Questionnaires differed by countries and by round.

Table A2: Countries per Afrobarometer Round

Country	R3	R4	R5	R6
Algeria			x	x
Benin	x	x	x	x
Botswana	x	x	x	x
Burkina		x	x	x
Burundi			x	x
Cameroon			x	x
Cape Verde	x	x	x	
Egypt			x	
Gabon				x
Ghana	x	x	x	x
Guinea			x	x
Kenya	x	x	x	x
Lesotho	x	x	x	x
Liberia		x	x	x
Madagascar	x	x	x	x
Malawi	x	x	x	x
Mali	x	x	x	x
Mauritius			x	
Morocco			x	x
Mozambique	x	x	x	x
Namibia	x	x	x	x
Niger			x	x
Nigeria	x	x	x	x
Senegal	x	x	x	x
Sierra Leone			x	x
South Africa	x	x	x	x
Sudan			x	x
Swaziland			x	
Tanzania	x	x	x	x
Togo			x	x
Tunisia			x	x
Uganda	x	x	x	x
Zambia	x	x	x	x
Zimbabwe	x	x	x	x

Table A3: Mines Status in Raw Minerals Database

Mine status	Observations	Percent
Active	357	25.89
Inactive	967	70.12
Care and maintenance	14	1.02
On hold awaiting financing	3	0.22
On hold awaiting higher prices	5	0.36
Rehabilitation	7	0.51
Temporarily on hold	19	1.38
Under litigation	7	0.51
Total	1,379	100

Note: The table excludes observations with missing values for mine status.

Table A4: Total Deposits by Mineral in Raw Minerals Database

	Mineral 1	Mineral 2	Mineral 3	Mineral 4	Mineral 5
Mineral	Gold	Coal	Diamonds	Copper	U308
N	522	145	138	115	84
Share	36.94	10.26	9.77	8.14	5.94
	Mineral 6	Mineral 7	Mineral 8	Mineral 9	Mineral 10
Mineral	Iron Ore	Platinum	Nickel	Phosphorus	Graphite
N	80	40	35	32	32
Share	5.66	2.83	2.48	2.26	2.26
Total N. Deposits	1417				
Share of Other Minerals	13.46				

Note: The table elaborates on information reported in the dataset geo-matching Afrobarometer observations to mineral deposits included in the Raw Materials Database. The information reports the total number of deposits for each mineral and the share.

Table A5: Robustness Checks: Fixed Effects

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Discuss politics				
Female X ActiveDeposit	0.046* (0.026)	0.047* (0.026)	0.047* (0.026)	0.047* (0.026)	0.050* (0.027)
Female	-0.223*** (0.006)	-0.222*** (0.006)	-0.222*** (0.006)	-0.223*** (0.006)	-0.224*** (0.006)
Deposit	0.043*** (0.011)	0.040*** (0.011)	0.034*** (0.011)	0.055** (0.022)	-0.032 (0.036)
ActiveDeposit	-0.087*** (0.022)	-0.084*** (0.022)	-0.078*** (0.022)	-0.078* (0.041)	-0.012 (0.082)
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mineral FE	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Location FE	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Mine FE	No	No	No	No	Yes
Observations	63092	61916	61916	61916	61915

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. Clustering at mine level. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion.
* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Table A6: USGS & Commodity Prices, Triple D-in-D, Main Mineral, Reg Year FE, District Clustering

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Discuss Politics	Voting	Community Meeting	Women Leaders	Protest
Within 20km USGS deposit	0.411 (0.271)	0.470*** (0.162)	-0.550 (0.465)	0.876*** (0.183)	0.246** (0.120)
Ln Price	0.088 (0.056)	0.087** (0.034)	-0.091 (0.095)	0.185*** (0.038)	0.048* (0.025)
USGS x Ln Price	-0.087 (0.056)	-0.093*** (0.034)	0.098 (0.095)	-0.181*** (0.038)	-0.050** (0.025)
Female	0.084 (0.136)	0.096 (0.085)	-0.385** (0.158)	1.084*** (0.128)	-0.097* (0.059)
USGS x Female	-0.306** (0.141)	-0.152* (0.089)	0.232 (0.167)	-1.127*** (0.133)	0.021 (0.062)
Female x Ln Price	-0.062** (0.028)	-0.024 (0.018)	0.045 (0.033)	-0.246*** (0.027)	0.014 (0.012)
USGS x Female x Ln Price	0.066** (0.029)	0.029 (0.018)	-0.045 (0.034)	0.235*** (0.027)	-0.007 (0.012)
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	82666	78800	83046	56553	81571

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. Clustering at region level. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Table A7: Low vs High Conflict Areas, No Protests

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Discuss politics	Voting	Community Meeting	Women Leaders	Protest
Panel A: Low Conflict					
Female	-0.216*** (0.015)	-0.063*** (0.010)	-0.027*** (0.009)	-0.138*** (0.017)	-0.029*** (0.006)
Deposit	0.032 (0.024)	-0.019 (0.015)	0.022 (0.014)	-0.009 (0.031)	-0.013 (0.012)
ActiveDeposit	-0.104** (0.049)	-0.007 (0.034)	-0.074** (0.032)	-0.082 (0.067)	0.002 (0.031)
Female X ActiveDeposit	0.072 (0.070)	0.129*** (0.037)	0.056 (0.039)	0.129** (0.063)	0.011 (0.028)
Observations	10338	8656	9960	10377	10197
Panel B: High Conflict					
Female	-0.222*** (0.012)	-0.077*** (0.009)	-0.009 (0.007)	-0.144*** (0.014)	-0.042*** (0.005)
Deposit	0.041* (0.021)	-0.044*** (0.014)	0.024* (0.013)	-0.053* (0.030)	-0.029*** (0.010)
ActiveDeposit	-0.093** (0.041)	0.028 (0.032)	-0.020 (0.031)	0.049 (0.071)	0.060*** (0.023)
Female X ActiveDeposit	0.060 (0.041)	0.004 (0.031)	0.001 (0.033)	0.036 (0.056)	-0.028 (0.021)
Observations	16177	14059	15267	16182	16027

Clustered standard errors in parentheses. Clustering at mine level. All regressions include controls for age, education and religion. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Low conflict (A) is defined at the median of the distribution (1 event in the last three years) and high conflict (B) is defined as above the median. Very high conflict (C) is defined as sample at the highest quintile of violence.